

MASTER'S THESIS

ON

**Influence of Online Marketing Strategies on the Sales
Success of B2B Companies**

**FOR THE PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT
FOR THE AWARD OF
MASTER OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION**

UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF

Faculty Mentor

Dr. Meenu Shant Priya
Associate Professor
GALGOTIAS UNIVERSITY

Submitted by

Sandeep Kumar
20GSOB2010091
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MBA 2020-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the Master's Thesis "Sandeep Kumar" has been prepared by Dr. Meenu Shant Priya under my supervision and guidance. The project report is submitted towards the partial fulfillment of 2 year, Full time Master of Business Administration.

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DECLARATION

I, Sandeep Kumar Roll No.20GSOB2010091, student of School of Business, Galgotias University, Greater Noida, hereby declare that the Master's Thesis on "**Influence of Online Marketing Strategies on the Sales Success of B2B Companies**" is an original and authenticated work done by me.

I further declare that it has not been submitted elsewhere by any other person in any of the institutes for the award of any degree or diploma.

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11/05/2022

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ABSTRACT

Digital marketing changes the way companies sell their products. Managers of B2B companies are looking for answers how to deploy digital marketing strategies to boost their sales success. There is scarce research on most suitable online promotional techniques with regard to the B2B segment therefore this thesis should provide an additional view on the topic. The theoretical part aims to understand digital marketing, sales success and B2B specifics. The second part focuses on the following research questions:

To understand the usage of online marketing strategies influence the success of B2B companies? What are the main goals that companies should strive to achieve in order to ensure success? What are key online marketing strategies for achieving the goals that lead to success? To understand the appropriate usage of online marketing ensure the success of B2B companies? A mixture of explorative and qualitative approach was used. The methodology for addressing the research questions varied from explaining key concepts, reviewing relevant literature and getting empirical interview data.

The analysis is based on semi-structured interviews with marketing agency decision makers, marketing professionals, B2B marketing strategists and senior sales managers in the geographical region of Slovenia and Austria.

Key contributions of the thesis can be summed up with the following facts:

Majority strongly agrees that digital marketing positively affects the success of B2B companies, Referrals and content marketing positively affect the revenue of B2B companies, Income generation and customer value are the most important company goals, Good corporate website, social media and SEO are crucial, The biggest budget share is allocated to digital advertising.

LIST OF KEY WORDS

AI: artificial intelligence

B2B: business-to-business

B2C: business to consumer

CM: content marketing

CLV: customer life value

CX: customer experience

Four C'S (4C) co-creation, currency, communal activation , conversation

Four P'S (4P) product, price, place, promotion.

IQ: interview question

PPC: pay per click

ROI: return on investment

RQ: research question

SEO: search engine optimization

SME: search engine marketing

SMB: small and medium size business

WOM: word of mouth

DM: digital marketing

INTRODUCTION

This master thesis aims to understand how companies should deploy digital marketing strategies to boost their sales success. The focus is on B2B companies, which all need to consider the following questions: How to deploy digital marketing strategies in the most efficient way? How to build a strong brand with the help of the digital environment? How should greater customer value be created? If marketers aspire to create new customer needs, what is the added value of digital marketing in this process? Why does B2B lag behind B2C? Why do some fail? Is there a trajectory? the context of the work, the research aims and objectives, the methodological approach and the structural overview of the thesis. the marketing as the activity of “engaging customers and managing profitable customer relationships.” The strategy of close alignment between the buyers’ needs and providers’ offers throughout the buying process has not changed much from the early beginnings. But progress has always been evolutionary and it has affected marketing as a whole, the way customer value is created and the way the return on investment is achieved. Keegan and Green (2019) see the first most fundamental change in the emergence of global markets. Technology and the Internet simply spurred activities even further. Brands are an important part of marketing. In today’s competitive environment brands thus play an important role since they are to differentiate themselves from anything already present on the market. McIntyre and Virzi (2021) however warn that managers’ favouring of brand awareness as their preferred strategic measure might be dangerous. It is not only the brand, it is also the perspective of the buyer. “The modern marketing era is driven by the self-educated buyer who marketers must engage to achieve a relevant, targeted, and value-based customer experience” (Oracle, 2021). This indicates that there should be a smart mix of traditional and digital strategies to influence the buyer so that he can make the most informed purchase decision. Presented content should be fact-based and credible. Murton Beets and Handley (2021) are convinced that content of higher quality and efficient product presentation surpass any strategy. Neither can this be improved much with best content distribution, targeting or content marketing technologies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concise literature review should not only provide better understanding of the topic and expose relevant recent research studies, but strive to answer some of the research questions. It might further on provide ideas for future research of most suitable marketing strategies. In the context of this thesis marketing strategy is a synonym for a set of marketing activities or tactics. There have been numerous definitions and defined elements comprising it. Varadarajan (2021) suggests to view it as “a pattern of decisions about products, markets, marketing activities and marketing resources in the processes of creation, communication and delivery of products.” It is interesting to follow how marketing managers allocate their budgets. In 2020 there are still many traditional channels, but digital ones are clearly front-ranked and in total represent two-thirds of the total spent (McIntyre & Virzi, 2021). Figure 1 presents the allocation of funds among fifteen different channels and marketing enablers: loyalty program management, event marketing, partner marketing, paid search, email marketing, content creation and management, SEO, mobile marketing, offline advertising, market research, social marketing, website, marketing and customer analytics, digital advertising, digital commerce. Why do digital channels rank so high? Managers estimate that digital marketing contributes to brand awareness and drives new business.

Despite the broad impact that digital marketing has, there is still a lack of knowledge about suitable online promotional techniques and strategies, especially with regard to B2B companies that do not have a strong brand.

Brosan (2021) assumes this might be due to the fact that so much of B2B activity is selective in its targeting, and is often commercially confidential.

This master thesis wants to create a solid body of research that will help marketing decision makers with informed value as well as ease the decision-making process.

The analytical part should provide a better insight into B2B companies and how they should utilize the digital tools in their promotion so as to comply with the goal of value creation for all stakeholders.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The author works in a young technological company that develops and produces hardware and software for access control, which is a narrow technological field of security systems and access management systems. The company is in the B2B segment and currently sells in , partly also in the market. There is still potential of future growth, especially when company's products converge with the field of IT or have advantageous technological and security features.

1. Consequently, it is the main role of the marketing and sales department to present the product value convincingly.
2. A new B2B partner should trust the brand, study it in detail and sell. In this particular case the sales and marketing process has not been exploited to its full potential.
3. The company struggles with getting new B2B partners in the global environment despite having a premium product line.
4. A similar struggle of how to better promote in order to gain new business clients can be seen at many B2B technological companies.
5. They frequently excel in developing products, but fail to promote them successfully and selling them profitably on a larger scale.
6. The industry standard and head toward a differentiated and industry-leading marketing strategy.
7. The researched topic only gains on its importance. This thesis should provide a solid theoretical background and relevant empirical data to help answer the set question of the manner in which industry standards can be surpassed and upgraded to the most relevant strategy.
8. The focus will be put on deployed marketing tactics and on finding why and how the online marketing strategies affect the (sales) success of companies. Since customer requirements constantly undergo changes and the information is gathered via different channels, it is important to understand how the purchase path has changed and what channels and activities lead to successful sales.

As mentioned in the introduction, the number of empirical analyses for the B2B segment is scarce. B2B marketing strategist Brosna (2021) states that there are “plentiful case studies for consumer-centric digital marketing, but less remains to be found in the B2B marketing community.” The critical overview and assessment of marketing tactics will give a range of insights on good practice. With the research of this thesis we hope to understand how B2B companies use digital marketing, what are the most important factors of digital marketing and how companies could perform better if they deployed most efficient tactics of digital marketing.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A mixture of explorative and qualitative approach will be used. Key concepts and terms will be defined and an in-depth literature review will be made. Currently most influential digital marketing tactics, the aspect of sales success and the specifics of B2B marketing will be analysed. The theoretical part will try to find correlation in available researches.

This chapter presents used methodology and instruments. The explanation of the data analysis approach, challenges and main issues are presented as well.

In preparation for defining our methodology, different research methods were reviewed. The chosen research design is a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches which is typical for social sciences and marketing research believes that in qualitative research generalizability and extensiveness is not the focus, but the goal is rather to be more intensive and gain access to cultural categories and assumptions. also state that qualitative methods are used when all endeavours are directed into problem understanding.

Research stages and goals

The research process with qualitative and quantitative techniques had the following stages:

- A. literature review to establish the theoretical background of the thesis (explorative approach)
- B. semi-structured interviews to verify the hypothesis established as part of the explorative approach, including the stages of (b1) interview design; (b2) entering the interview into the online format for computer-aided personalized interviews; (b3) defining focus group or interview targets; (b4) inviting targets for participation; (b5) running interviews and transcribing feedback of open-ended questions.
- C. data analysis and interpretation.

Research goals were the following:

- profound understanding of the researched topic
- gathering detail-rich, grounded qualitative data with insider's perspective
- answering research questions via individual interpretations of interviewees
- verifying answers of research questions with theoretical background
- collecting precise research data that is easier to analyse
- recognizing patterns in interviews by means of quantitative content analysis
- finding best practices for B2B segment

Research questions

For the purpose of the research there were four research questions formulated. The main research question should cover a broader topic of digital marketing strategies and the success of B2B companies. Further three research questions should focus on several aspects of the relation between digital marketing and the success of B2B companies.

Main research question

(RQ1): To understand the usage of online marketing strategies influence the success of B2B companies?

Digital marketing has gained on its importance for B2B and B2C companies. The online environment is not only used to present a company, but to sell products or services, build brands, communicate with customers and to focus on offering clear customer value. Because traditional marketing is often too expensive, the digital marketing might present a cheaper and more efficient alternative. The aim was to find out how much digital marketing contributes to the sales success of B2B companies.

(RQ2): What are the main goals that companies should strive to achieve in order to ensure success?

The second research question aims to explore what is understood under the term success and what strategic directives should companies follow to be regarded as successful.

(RQ3): What are key online marketing strategies for achieving the goals that lead to success?

The third research question should precisely check what are the most efficient digital marketing activities. Recent researches and categories presented in these surveys were used as a guideline when formulating interview questions.

(RQ4): How can appropriate usage of online marketing ensure the success of B2B companies?

With the last research question we wanted the respondents to personally evaluate two specific categories that literature and surveys define as the most important: website and content.

In the semi-structure interview format both closed and open-ended questions were used. The closed question should provide statistically more valid data that can be easily aggregated, whereas open-ended questions contribute to the qualitative sphere of the research. Closed-type questions were used with an increasing five-level Likert type scale in order to rate the level of non-importance or importance (with marks from 1 to 5 (1 showing non-importance and 5 showing great importance), the option 6 was given as a not-possible-to-estimate or do-not-knowoption.

The interview questions are author's work since there was no similar questionnaire available. The questions were, however, based on theory and research presented in the literature review in Chapter 2. Table 4 provides an background overview for the setting of questions. At the same time Table 4 presents how the main research questions were verified with corresponding interview questions and how these were to be verified with individual replies by interviewees.

Methods used:	RQ1	RQ2	RQ3	RQ4
Literature study	X	X	X	X
Research papers	X	X	X	X

Surveys	X		X	
Expert consulting companies reviews	X	X	X	X
Interview	X	X	X	X

TABLE 1: METHODOLOGY FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Classes	Likert Scale	Average Mean	Standard Deviation	Content analysis	Data presentation
IQ1	X	X	X		graph
IQ2	X	X	X		graph
IQ3				x	table, word cloud
IQ4	X	X	X		graph
IQ5	X	X	X		graph
IQ6	X	X	X		graph
IQ7	X	X	X		graph
IQ8	X	X	X		graph
IQ9				x	table, word cloud
IQ10	X				pie chart
IQ11	X				graph
IQ12	X				graph

TABLE 2: TYPES OF RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND DATA PRESENTATION

Table 1 shows what methods were used for what research questions. Expert consulting companies refer to established institutions such as Gartner or McKinsey. Exact literature references, surveys, research papers can be found in Chapters 1 and 2, in Table 3 and among bibliographical references.

Table 2 shows different types of used analyses and how the obtained data is presented. Some of the research questions will be partially answered by means of studying the theoretical background. An attempt will be made to grasp the underlying connections between digital marketing and sales and to transfer knowledge with insights into the research.

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

The thesis initiates with a comparison of traditional and digital marketing, an overview of digital marketing goals and metrics, as well as current strategies in the realm of the digital. Since the digital environment is where the B2C segment thrives, it is interesting to draw parallels where the most influential tactics are discussed. covers the question of success, or better sales success. There is a myriad of factors that contribute to this. Generally, a company following three main goals i.e. income generation, brand building, creating customer value, could reach the point of success on a long-term basis.

The research of B2B marketing strategies and the specifics of the B2B business. There are some fundamental changes in the B2B segment especially in terms of CX (customer experience) as well, the main research is narrowed just on the online or digital sphere that still has relatively little research behind, but gains its value in professional surveys and hence should not be neglected. The most successful practices will also be reviewed.

The analytical part should give a deeper understanding of the researched topic within the set entrepreneurial environment of Slovene and Austrian companies that either struggle to sell well in the Slovenian or pan-European market.

Finally, the conclusion should bring a better understanding of the currently most influential online tactics (for B2B companies) in terms of increasing sales and gaining on brand reputation that might be co-contributing to the sales success in the long term.

Traditional versus digital marketing

If marketers aspire to create new customer needs, what is the added value of digital marketing? Traditional marketing with printed marketing material reaches a limited audience, it can serve a global market and it is rarely specifically targeted. It also cannot be changed once it is printed and leads to delayed seller-consumer communication. This marketing approach starts with segmentation and targeting, brand positioning and differentiation, 4P concept and the aim of value-creating services or products (Figure 2). Digital marketing on the other hand refers to the ways consumers are reached via digital channels. Yasmin et. al (2021) state that the term refers also to the promotion on mobile phones, social media, display advertising as well as search engine marketing, therefore promotion via digital technologies might be a better definition.

The attempt of selling items on the internet started thirty years ago and with it also the digital, initially electronic, marketing phenomena, as well as the digitally empowered buyer (Minculete & Olar, 2021). Today digital disruption forces companies to transform their marketing if they wish to successfully manage a portfolio of profitable offerings. "Digital is just one aspect of marketing, one element of the promotional mix" states Charlesworth (2020). Kotler, Kartajaya and Setiawan (2021) on the other hand claim that "the two should coexist with interchanging roles across the customer path" as is shown in Figure 2 below. Figure 2 also presents a comparison of both types of marketing. The authors see in traditional and digital marketing the same goal, namely to attract potential clients and to improve a brand image, but point out the difference in tactics. The digital world does not exclude the input of potential clients or the online community that can be regarded as a single segment now.

Further on, the traditional vertical relationship between brands and consumers changed into a horizontal one: clients and brands are befriended, clients accept different brand imagery. The traditional four P's were redefined into a connected marketing mix or the four C's:

- 1) co-creation as the new product development strategy,
- 2) currency with an exemplary dynamic pricing for greater profitability,
- 3) communal activation with peer-to-peer distribution and
- 4) conversation that is frequently platform-based.

The newly coined term marketing 4.0 incorporates the main ideas presented above and the ultimate goal of winning customer advocacy. In terms of relevance, the curated content with enhanced relevance to micro niches might be the most influential. Forbes warns also about the gap between hype and reality especially with regard to technologies that consume and produce data in the form of over generalized analyses that might mislead to inappropriate marketing tactics. Kotler and Armstrong (2020) coined the phrase omni-channel retailing that should present an efficient and balanced marketing strategy for the future or a “seamless cross-channel buying experience that integrates in-store, online, and mobile shopping.”

FIGURE 2: INTERCHANGING ROLES OF TRADITIONAL AND DIGITAL MARKETING

Customers find digital marketing advantageous since they stay updated with products, they engage more, get precise information and prices that can be compared with competitive products, they make immediate purchase and share their experience or content of products. It is interesting to see that consumer product brands spent the most on digital advertising. Companies in the B2B segment allocate 50 % of their marketing budget into traditional channels (customer and industry events, sponsorships, traditional media) and the second half into digital ones. Technological companies, on the other hand, switch the ratio and prefer the digital marketing with 60 % budget allocation. Figure 3 presents ranking of twelve digital channels for B2B marketers.

FIGURE 3: TWELVE DIGITAL CHANNELS OF B2B

Two less formal terms need to be mentioned as well since they are frequently used in connection with digital or online marketing industry: Martech (marketing technology) and Adtech (advertising technology), the wrapper for contextual marketing that should deliver engaging and relevant experiences as demanded by today’s customers.

FIGURE 4: ADTECH AND MARTECH CONVERGENCE REVOLUTIONIZE MARKETING

This shift will be focused on quality rather than scale (Figure 4). Gartner on the other hand, is more sceptical foreseeing technical and financial impediments that stand in the way of fast convergence.

Digital marketing strategies

Digital advertising across national boundaries and the mobility of consumers have created opportunities for marketers to pursue pan-regional product positioning (Keegan & Green, 2021), therefore these marketing strategies differ from the traditional ones. Speaking in favour of online advertising: 30% of marketers rate paid advertising in the form of printed or broadcasted media .

FIGURE 5: BUYER JOURNEY MAP WITH TOUCHPOINT

As shown in Forrester’s Figure 5 above the importance of digital marketing parallelly grows in two dimensions: (1) when the customer’s path gradually evolves from the stage of awareness, appeal, asking, acting to the final state of advocacy, (2) when the brand improves on its competitiveness and passes the level of enjoyment, experience until finally reaching the level of engagement. Forrester finds that a business buyer controls the buying process more than the seller controls the selling process. The purchase path is more complex and involves different touchpoints where traditional marketing is a minority channel (Figure 4).

The six most important online marketing strategies are presented below (Hutt & Speh, 2021, Kotler & Armstrong, 2020). Next to that there are also: online PR (increasing brand awareness and backlinks to a site), display or interactive advertising, online partnerships that include link building, affiliate marketing, online sponsorship and co-branding, development of micro sites, mobile applications and mobile messaging. The proportions of usage varies among marketeers, nevertheless they should be coextensively used for the most efficient targeting, with a suitable message and at the right time.

Content marketing (CM) is defined by Content Marketing Institute as a marketing technique of creating and distributing valuable, relevant and consistent content to attract and acquire a clearly defined audience, with the objective of driving profitable customer action. Kotler and Armstrong (2021) add the goals of inspiring customers for a particular brand and sharing brand messages “across a fluid mix of paid, owned, earned, and shared channels. find that CM affects low- and high-level accounts as sales leads. It plays a complementary role to the existing sales force and helps generating new sales leads and works especially well in the B2B realm.

Corporate website is a convenient, credible message board for an online promotion of a company and its product portfolio. It is one of the first go-to resources consulted in the purchase decision-making process and customers browse it to identify and qualify sellers. Branded web communities that present engaging brand content and create customer–brand community, blogs or forums should be mentioned here as well (Kotler & Armstrong, 2021).

Email marketing is one of the communication tools to deliver a business message. Targeted, personalized direct mail messages and newsletters are aimed at building a relationship with consumers

and motivating them for a purchase. It is the third most important marketing tools for B2B companies. **Social media marketing** approaches engage business customers and manage customer relationships anywhere, anytime (Kotler & Armstrong, 2022) by enhancing brand relevance and providing exposure (Keegan & Green, 2021). More control and access to important information is given to both parties. LinkedIn, for example, has become the third most frequently used sales channel following telephone and direct email.

By using sight, motion and sound **online videos** and **webinars** are an efficient tool for products that need to be demonstrated. With real-time customer support or option to provide input on product features they can be regarded as interactive learning tools.

Search engine marketing (SEM) refers to “placing messages on a search engine, encouraging click-through to a web site when the user types a specific keyword phrase”(Chaffey & Smith, 2021). With two disciplines (1) SEO with on- and off-site ranking factors and (2) PPC it increases a site's visibility through organic search engines results and advertising.

Two-thirds of B2B marketers have adopted also **programmatic advertising**, and more than 70 percent intend to invest more into this field. Dun and Bradstreet, however, warn that they should be aware of the fact that this strategy does not automatically drive leads when analytics and data sets are poor, audience is incorrectly targeted and KPIs are inappropriately set.

Digital marketing framework and most important goals

In order to find the right strategy to achieve success three questions need to be asked: Where are we today? Where do we want to go? What do we need to get to the final goal? Chaffey and Smith (2021) add to the *situation analysis*, *definition of objectives* and *strategy* - above presented as three questions - also the notions of *tactics*, *actions* and *control* that correspond to the following questions: Which tactical tools do we use to implement strategy? Which action plans are required to implement strategy? How do we manage the strategy process? This is presented with the SOSTAC® model (Figure 6).

Objectives of digital marketing: (1) branding, (2) revenue generation and (3) customer care.

Omobono (2021) analysed the most important B2B marketing priorities and the goal of raising brand awareness was positioned second (after deepening customer relationship) while having the highest index out of seven highlighted tasks for 2021. Online presence complements and enhances branding efforts of a company and is a constituent element of an overall branding strategy. A brand needs to be suitably positioned in order to convey a convincing message for the consumer. Precise differentiation through its marketing mix contributes to brand integrity and trust on the consumers' side. Online presence enhances supporting service for the consumer and improves customer experience. It also acts as an acquisition channel that generates revenue by making direct sales or leads (Kotler et al., 2021). Customer prioritization can lead profitable sales and next to deploying CRM, statistical and data-mining packages Mahadevan and Kettinger (2021) suggest a service oriented model that exploits dynamic

customer relationships via customer service personnel. Marketing departments should not lack people with a complete skill-set of: marketing knowledge, experience in analytics, lead generation, quality delivery of digital service .

FIGURE 6: SOSTAC® PLANNING FRAMEWORK FOR DIGITAL MARKETING

Digital marketing metrics

Explain the term of marketing ROI as “the net return from a marketing investment divided by the costs of the marketing investment,” but authors also agree that there is no consistent definition. It should measure profits generated by investments into marketing activities.

Rust, Lemon and introduced a model of marketing ROI that can be applied to the digital marketing as well. Figure 7 shows a data-driven framework for analyzing the impact of competing marketing expenditures and for projecting the ROI that will result from the expenditures.

(CLV), which in turn increases company's overall customer equity. Increased customer equity, in relation to the cost of the marketing investments, determines return on marketing investment.

FIGURE 7: MODEL FOR MARKETING RETURN ON INVESTMENT

Digital footprint is the basis of digital marketing metrics and analytics. minculete and Olar (2018) state that among various types of marketing good measurability is crucial. This speaks in favour of digital marketing that has several metrics and these vary from channel to channel.

the most frequent **online metrics** are: *total visits, new sessions, channel-specific traffic* (direct, referrals, organic, social count as the most important ones), *bounce rate, lead-to-close ratio, customer retention rate, customer value, cost per lead, projected return on investment* and *total conversions* as one of the most important metrics measuring the profitability of overall marketing efforts. The author summarizes that some of the metrics might be misinterpretations of website performance rather than indications of user behaviour. Kotler, Kartajaya and Setiawan (2021) point out also the importance of the marketing productivity metrics PAR (purchase action ratio) and BAR (brand advocacy ratio). "PAR measures how good companies convert people who are aware of them into purchase decisions and BAR measures how good companies convert people who are aware of them into loyal advocates."

Relationship measures such as *customer satisfaction*, *engagement*, *retention* and *equity* are evaluated under the umbrella of relationship marketing that recognizes the long-term value of customer

relationships and extends communication beyond intrusive advertising and sales promotional messages (Palmatier, 2021). Customer satisfaction, commitment, trust and involvement are antecedents to customer engagement that can run on cognitive, emotional or behavioural level. Further on, customer equity with three drivers (value, brand, relationship) would be regarded a consequence of customer engagement.

FIGURE 8: FRAMEWORK FOR RESEARCH IN DIGITAL MARKETING

In terms of analysing the online data, the most popular is the commercial platform of Google Analytics. Similarly, Facebook, LinkedIn provide analytics for commercial users of the platform, but companies frequently decide for proprietary software that enables analytics as a full service offering (e.g. Oracle Infinity). As part of analytics lead scoring predictive analytics generate some of the biggest excitement. Kardon (2021) point out that artificial intelligence is able to identify prospective leads across multiple touch points (e.g. trade show visit, visit of a company website, webinar watching, marketing email reading) and correspondingly prioritize efforts. Further on, author maintains that similarly to prospect touch points, purchasing decisions are also a multifaceted aspect of buyer behavior with multiple stakeholders. A Gartner study found the average number of people involved in B2B purchase decisions is 6.8.

Kannan and Li (2021) developed a framework for research in digital marketing (Figure 8). It shows connections among stakeholders, as well as defines outcomes that can be regarded as metrics (value for customer, customer value for the company and company's value).

To sum up, digital marketing is often referred to as data-driven marketing, but offline and online gathered data should be combined owing to the fact that digital data is light on specific detail, whereas up to date offline sources are rich in detail.

Appropriate usage of online marketing strategies and their influence

Best application of online marketing strategies should lead to loyal and profitable customers. Customer loyalty is defined as willingness to advocate a brand. Kotler, Kartajaya and Setiawan (2021) believe that the customer's path to the state of loyalty and advocacy is made of two phases, namely the pre-connectivity and the connectivity era. In the primary phase customers pass the stage of brand awareness (their personal attitude toward a brand), attitude changing and acting. As soon as the second phase starts, the initial brand's appeal is already influenced by the surrounding community. As shown in Figure 9 customer behaviour changes throughout five stages (five A's: aware, appeal, ask, act, advocate), enabling various touch points and leading to corresponding five key impressions. Customers first (1) *know*, then they (2) *like* something, afterwards they are (3) convinced, decide to (4) buy and lastly advocate or (5) recommend brands. The entire process is not a straightforward one. Depending on how loyal customers connect among each other and thus build ask-and-advocate relationship the brand appeal strengthens or weakens.

FIGURE 9: CUSTOMER'S PATH IN THE CONNECTIVITY ERA WITH FIVE A STAGES

Sales success

Marketing with a high extent of market knowledge and sales are closely linked. Gartner points out that sales and digital should run parallelly so as to support the customer's journey. Le Meunier-FitzHugh and Piercy (2021) prove that there is a direct, positive relationship between marketing and sales. There are five antecedents for better collaboration, namely a positive senior management attitude, reduction of interdepartmental conflict, better communication, establishment of organizational learning and effective market intelligence systems. Others dispute the importance of sales-marketing cooperation in the implementation stage, but speak in favour of that in the concept development stage.

What goals need to be pursued to gain success?

If productivity is company's enhancer of success, focus should be put on increasing attraction, commitment, affinity and optimizing curiosity (Kotler et. al, 2021). Basic marketing goals include

(1) income generation, (2) brand development, good customer service and thus (3) improved customer value. It is difficult to find and assess all goals that a company can have in order to deem its operation successful, the focus here will be put on the mentioned three goals that are the most predominant ones.

Goal 1: income generation

Marketing, either in traditional or digital form, manages profitable customer relationships (Kotler et al., 2021). In order to generate (1) profitable sales results and fulfill the set goals, the sales channels should be properly designed. Customer segments and exact needs ought to be defined, potentials per segment estimated and competitors need to be benchmarked. Companies should also prepare solutions for customers' latent needs in order to realize potential sales in the future. The inability to evaluate selected channel options might be of big disadvantage since it can lead to missed future business opportunities. There are many impeding factors or circumstances that negatively affect revenue generation, such as poor products, non-motivating teams, lack of expert personnel, aggressive competition, low funds, negative economic and political conditions, poor reputation or similar, but if the basic sales preconditions are not met, the sales mechanism that fuels any company's operation cannot generate sufficient income.

Goal 2: brand building

The second important goal is brand building (2). Visconti & Van Laer (2021) open an issue that is particularly interesting for this research with the claim that "a lot of brand content online remains unobserved due to a lack of storytelling). Branding is said to upgrade something common into more valuable and meaningful (Kotler & Pfoertsch, 2021), it facilitates the identification of products, services and businesses as well as differentiates them from the competition.

Moreover, brands help people make purchase decisions and do not only create awareness, but give a brand promise. This could be interpreted as a two-step process of showing trust:

- (a) Initial choice after having evaluated competition's offerings.
- (b) Long-term trust and recommendation. It also presents an opportunity for establishing enduring, competitive advantages, as well as creating company's most important and sustainable asset.

The branding principle that companies should follow are: consistency, clarity, constancy, visibility, and authenticity. Since brand image encompasses a holistic interpretation of consumers about a brand, it is crucial to understand and correctly manage the brand image that indirectly affects also the satisfaction of customer needs. If parallels are drawn between a brand and a website, we could assume that a bigger visitor number contributes to brand development and the number of returning visitors spending more time on site might indicate their status of affiliation and advocacy.

Goal 3: customer value

Frequently the following question is asked: What affects digital environment most? Strategy, technology or people? People and coherent teams could be the key to good customer service, lasting customer relationships and thus (3) improved customer value. How can customer value be improved? “Each customer’s lifetime value (CLV) results from the frequency of category purchases, average quantity of purchase, and brand-switching patterns combined with the firm’s contribution margin” (Rust, et al. 2021).

People are sharp in targeting suitable clients, profitably satisfying customer needs on a high-quality level and motivating teams internally. According to Digital Marketing Institute (2016) the fast evolving digital landscape requires to upskill and professionally develop teams with knowledge of the digital. They report “digital skills gaps on a global level, across many industries, within organizations of all sizes and in employees of varying ages”. Therefore trainings on digital environment should be an important part of a corporate strategy.

Other important factors affecting sales success are: market research and interviews, defining focus groups, analysing what could be improved to sell more. These activities should be part of an ongoing process. Another important dimension of the success formula is time. Companies

need to have a timeline and the delivery of results in the shortest period possible. Investopedia defines marketing as a long-term, multiple-touch process that leads to sales growth over time.

B2B aspect

B2B environment typically has strong offline relationship between the buyer and seller (Charlesworth, 2022), however, advances in digital marketing techniques remain largely unexploited (Mero et al., 2021). As researched by the agency McKinsey (2020) management practices related also to the digital strategy strongly correlate with growth and profitability. As seen on the Figure 10 below the B2C segment with the average digital quotient score of 35 supersedes the B2B segment. The digital quotient is an average across 4 equally weighted dimensions: culture, strategy, capabilities, organization.

FIGURE 10: DIGITAL QUOTIENT SCORE ON A SCALE FROM 0 TO 100 FOR B2B (30%) AND B2C COMPANIE

B2B objectives and priorities

Omobono (2021) has surveyed American and European B2B market professionals announcing a change of B2B fundamentals. The digital transformation should shape business strategies, nurture talents and company cultures. CX ranks as the leading objective (49%). Next is a strategic brand with brand awareness rooted in the business strategy and operational activities. Further on, marketing should function as an accelerator for customer service, HR, sales, operations and IT.

Figure 11 shows marketing priorities for B2B marketing professionals. Interestingly, the goal of developing brand position grew with the highest rate (from 9% to 39% in seven years). 85% of respondents agreed that communicating a clear brand vision would be the most intensive activity in 2020. The agency Omobono warns not to underestimate the importance of understanding the target market. Interestingly, larger organisations ranked deepening customer relationships first.

FIGURE 11: MARKETING PRIORITIES 2019 FOR B2B MARKETING PROFESSIONALS

B2B elements of value

A survey by the agency Bain & Company Inc (2021) showed that B2B offerings are more commoditized, and selling such products can now have some emotional components as well,

Meeting specifications at an acceptable price in compliance with regulations while abiding by ethical standards are basic values. Above are the most popular functional elements addressing economic or product performance needs (cost reduction, scalability). Elements within the third level ease doing business by increasing productivity, improving operational performance, on the other hand there are the first subjective elements, namely enhancers of relationships between parties. The fourth level brings more additional types of subjective value, addressing individual buyers' priorities. These elements of value can address highly emotional concerns (e.g. fear of inappropriate purchase affecting revenues). Some vendors manage to greatly benefit by offering risk reduction and reputational assurance to individuals accountable for purchases.

FIGURE 12: B2B ELEMENTS OF VALUE

B2B most effective marketing channels

"B2B players that embed digital in their go-to-market programs grow more than five times faster than their peers and have 30 percent higher acquisition efficiency" (McKinsey & Company, 2021). According to Charlesworth (2021) B2B digital channels with the most positive impact on revenue (approximately 10% per channel) are: CM and SEO, email marketing and search advertising. It is interesting to see that social media makes almost 50% lower impact than search advertising. It seems that B2B environment still appreciates many traditional channels: referrals are twice as much important as CM and SEO, but it is surprising to see how high digital channels are positioned.

	<i>Marketing activities/ channels used to acquire customers (%)</i>	<i>Activity/channel which makes the most positive impact on revenue (%)</i>
Email marketing	88.6	8.3
Social media	85.0	3.1
Content marketing	81.2	9.1
Search engine optimization	78.0	9.1
Word-of-mouth/referrals	74.9	22.0
Conference/trade shows	74.5	9.1
Search advertising	59.6	6.7
Public relations	59.2	1.2
Outbound calling	58.0	8.3
Retargeting	52.5	0.8
Partner marketing	48.6	5.1
Display advertising	47.5	0.8
Video advertising	22.0	0.8
TV, radio and print ads	12.5	0.4
Other	5.5	4.3

TABLE 3: THE MOST POPULAR AND EFFECTIVE B2B MARKETING CHANNELS

An analysis of a large consulting service provider showed that digital events and digital content can create sales leads and positively affect low- and high-level account employees without any in-person events (Wang et al., 2021). When high account participate in digital events, the number of sales leads or won opportunities greatly increases.

B2B and B2C survey similarly shows that ratings of channel effectiveness shift. Email marketing is still the most influential tool, but its importance is falling. CM, social media and online video/podcasts/webinars on the other hand have increased for more than 20% per individual channel.

B2B online

It is important to be well acquainted with digital tactics for the B2B environment. The buying cycle is namely a long, arduous process, driven by multiple stakeholders with different agendas. the company and its product portfolio. Companies should be aware that website needs to be tailored to both end users, as well as decision makers, while addressing relevant verticals without alienating any of them.

Company websites need to incorporate three critical design elements: (1) give customers an entry point on their own terms, (2) share solutions in their language, (3) help customers do the purchase or find sought information. Charlesworth (2018) defines various stages in the B2B buying process that digital marketers can address on the website:

1. **Problem** recognition. Since buyers use the web to be updated with news in their sector, online press releases about developments or new products should be presented on the company's local website as well as distributed to industry-specific sites that might be visited by industry professionals. Such content might prompt the B2B buyer to recognize that they have a problem.
2. **Solution** to the problem. Product specifications addressing any problem issue should be clearly presented on the company's website to stay in touch with developments in their industry that may influence any specification decisions.
3. **Search** for products or suppliers. With search engine optimization the information that buyers seek must be made easily available on the site.
4. **Online evaluation** of products or suppliers. Websites are the first point of business contact and the first perception of the product, therefore the importance of quality content, consolidated brand and professional image should not be underestimated.
5. **Online purchase** is not the norm in a B2B, however, a retail-style (complex password-protected order form or a personalized web site) site might be appropriate.
6. **After-sales service** can be a specific objective of company's online presence. Installation instructions or application updates can for example be presented.

B2B websites are substantially less usable and extremely specialized with complex specifications. Nielsen's test (2020) of around 200 B2B sites points out good design elements: efficient navigation, useful product descriptions, informative comparison charts, enticing up-sells, helpful support, instructive white papers and similar.

A B2B buyer might on the other hand already have brand affinity. Kotler and Pfoertsch (2021) dispute the idea that B2B branding is not relevant and that products are chosen through an objective decision-making process that only accounts for the so-called hard facts like features. Due to the fact that inspecting, sampling, risk avoidance and negotiation are integral aspects of B2B buying, the website should provide a B2B buyer with sufficient and relevant background information. All buying criteria should be addressed without emotions: exact product specifications and applications, lead times, delivery schedules, shipping costs, compliance with regulations. Some B2B providers prefer to display price and discount structures offline.

B2B content marketing

B2B purchase decisions are greatly affected by online presentations and this is where digital content should lead potential buyers. Content marketing (CM) presents a cultural change from "selling" to "helping". B2B digital CM with useful, relevant, compelling and timely content is a useful tool for achieving and sustaining trusted brand status. It should be viewed as an integral part of overall marketing and sales activities that can also be automated to generate high-quality sales leads through behavioral targeting and content personalization. These activities can be in-person events (conferences with personal contacts with client), digital events (webinars) or posting company-generated content on branded websites (Wang et. al, 2019).

Best practices

The choice of best practices varies individually, per segment, per business verticals, experience or many other factors. This section presents three concepts or novelties that might aid in optimizing digital marketing processes, generating better income, building the brand and creating greater customer value: (1) blueprints, (2) strategy alignment and (3) AI.

FIGURE 13: IDENTIFYING POPULAR TOUCHPOINTS AND CHANNELS

Strategy alignment

Despite better access to information across multiple digital channels and peers, purchase can take much longer than in the past. Even after a sales pitch, customers return to digital channel to validate vendor’s claims. (Jordan, 2021). Surprisingly, Gartner research found that 83% of surveyed customers accessed digital channels even in the late purchasing stages. This highlights the need to have a digital marketing strategy specifically designed to help buyers through the early, middle and late stages of the purchase process. Integrated B2B marketing strategy should be aligned with strategic business objectives. B2B personal selling needs to be supported and supplemented by digital marketing since it is able to reach not only direct clients, but also buying influentials and potential buyers (Hutt & Speh, 2021). High-quality customer engagement requires a corresponding omnichannel strategy, qualified and experienced commerce professionals, customer-focused mindset, integrated technology platform and the openness of sellers to engage with experienced ecosystem partners and learn from their experience (Forrester, 2020).

Dun and Bradstreet suggest that B2B marketers should deploy account-based marketing to improve customer engagement, improve go-to-market efficiencies, increase revenue generation, and achieve higher ROI. Jordan (2018) concludes that 88% of account managers believe servicing accounts above and beyond customer expectations is the surest way to grow. Although better-than-expected customer service helps retain a sales account, research shows it doesn’t actually impact the degree to which the account grows.

Is AI the future?

Eighty percent of B2B marketing executives believe AI will revolutionize current marketing strategies and make them more intuitive, smarter and more efficient. High-performing companies are more than twice as likely to use AI for data collection, lead scoring or B2B consumers’ choices and direct them. It will surely improve CX, but it will also open the dilemma where does consumer’s privacy end.

The value of B2B platforms

World Economic Forum (2021) started an interesting digital marketing incentive with B2B digital platforms that enable partnerships across vast ecosystems and could create \$10 trillion of value for business and wider society in this decade. Value is created based on trust, non-linearly in an iterative manner across entire ecosystems. This might not only lead to the reshaping of how marketing is done, but also how industries are defined.

The main research question (RQ1): How does the usage of online marketing strategies influence the success of B2B companies? was tested with interview questions IQ2 and IQ6.

FIGURE 14: DIGITAL MARKETING POSITIVELY IMPACTS COMPANY SUCCESS (ANSWERS TO IQ2)

The respondents to rate how positively marketing activities impact their company's revenue. This was an interesting question that verified the affect of traditional and digital marketing approaches. In the theoretical part it was pointed out by several researchers that the best way is to combine both approaches while having in mind all steps of the purchase path of today's informed buyer. The first traditional activity is on the fourth place, however, this does not diminish its major importance that was exposed by respondents among the open-ended questions or comments. Maybe the results would have been slightly more in favour of customer contact if respondents were solely from technology industry.

FIGURE 15: MARKETING ACTIVITIES POSITIVELY IMPACT REVENUE (ANSWERS TO IQ6)

Table 5 below shows that the first three activities have the highest average and also the lowest standard deviations. It is interesting to see that the standard deviation value for *customer visits* is also relatively low. One of the surprising elements of the research is that marketing automation software ranks so low. It also has the highest standard deviation. As presented in the theoretical part, trend predictors define it as the ultimate marketing tool for the future. It might be concluded that respondents have not come across this novelty yet, or maybe it is being used only by the companies that can afford expensive marketing tools.

FIGURE 16: IMPORTANT COMPANY GOALS FOR SUCCESS (ANSWERS TO IQ)

FIGURE 17: DIGITAL CHANNELS INFLUENCE SALES (ANSWERS TO IQ4)

According to average values *good corporate website* is on the first place (average 4,5, standard deviation 0,82), this is followed by *social media* (average 4,3, standard deviation 0,79), *SEO* (average 4,3, standard deviation 1,16) and *PPC* (average 4,2, standard deviation 0,98). Only on the fifth place we find content marketing that the recent survey of Omobono (2020) exposes as the most influential channel for B2B. However, corporate website is also the second most important channel for the mentioned survey. On the account of that we can say that we have partly verified the available research. Surprisingly social media ranked quite high and this might also be partly biased with our sample

IQ5 checked the allocation of budgets among several digital channels, offline advertising or any individual channel that respondents' companies might use. Figure 18 shows allocations for all channels ordered by categories. Values in each linear bar are averages. Detailed average values and standard deviations can be checked in Appendix 1. We can see that ten respondents mostly invest into *digital advertising* (19,9%). Interestingly *offline advertising* (13,1%) is still strongly present and is placed second. On the third and fourth place are again important digital marketing channels: *social marketing* with 13% and *content marketing* with 11,5%. If a comparison is made with Gartner's study of budget allocation by marketing channels (Figure 1), a relatively big discrepancy can be seen in the top.

FIGURE 18: DIGITAL MARKETING BUDGET ALLOCATION (ANSWERS TO IQ5)

Gartner’s study positioned digital commerce first, digital advertising second, marketing and customer analytics third and website fourth. This might be due to the fact that their focus group were B2B and B2C companies. However, their high ranking of customer and marketing analytics does indicate that our respondents should in the future invest more into this channel (ranked third lowest, Figure 18) since knowing the informed customer well will be a big competitive advantage in the future.

FIGURE 19: WEBSITE ELEMENTS THAT INFLUENCE PURCHASE (ANSWERS TO IQ7)

Chapter 2.4.5 presents the importance of content marketing for B2B companies and IQ8 should verify with the interviewees what types of content is mostly used for this purpose in their companies. Several answers were possible. Figure 20 shows the most important elements. Values in each linear bar are frequencies.

FIGURE 20: CONTENT TYPES USED FOR PROMOTION (ANSWERS TO IQ8)

Detailed average values and standard deviations can be checked in Appendix 1. *Social media posts*, *videos* and *photos* were the most frequent choice by eleven respondents. Next to that, two respondents mentioned a *proprietary content hub* aiming to provide customer-relevant content and increase brand loyalty. Another respondent mentioned their focus on *news articles*, *webinars* and *researches*.

IQ9, where we ask for individual opinions on the importance of digital marketing for B2B, is interpreted in section 4.3.

Qualitative research

For the content analysis of two open-ended questions IQ3 and IQ9 the free tool Atlasti available at <https://atlasti.com/> was used. The qualitative research is expanded with quotes from transcripts that support the research arguments and bring some interesting ideas to the forefront. It can be concluded that the results of IQ3 and IQ9 partly answer two research questions (RQ2, RQ4). We were looking for the main goals leading to success and what online tactics are efficient for B2B companies. The first part of the answer is in the word cloud below and the second one in the overview of most significant quotations that expose not only the specifics of B2B, but also the trends that we can expect in the future.

Content analysis

The content analysis helped us analyse interview data when open-ended questions were used (IQ3, IQ9). This approach, sometimes called coding, enables simplification of data and their conversion into a more structured form. Transcripts were categorised into themes according to research questions. Further on, terms were chosen denoting these themes. For each term a specific term list was made. Results are structurally presented below.

IQ3											
Value	Increase				Result			Steady			
brand	8	1,10%	better	4	0,55%	income	3	0,41%	same	2	0,27%
customer	7	0,96%	growth	2	0,27%	revenue	3	0,41%	stagnation	1	0,14%
value	14	1,92%	big	1	0,14%	winning	1	0,14%	smaller	1	0,14%
client	1	0,14%	premium	1	0,14%	success	1	0,14%	conservati	1	0,14%
price	1	0,14%	rapid	1	0,14%	successft	1	0,14%	traditional	1	0,14%
mix	1	0,14%	more	10	1,37%	awards	1	0,14%	slightly	1	0,14%
multitude	1	0,14%	new	1	0,14%						
combine	1	0,14%	improve	1	0,14%						
TOTAL	34	4,66%	TOTAL	21	2,88%	TOTAL	10	1,37%	TOTAL	7	0,96%

TABLE 6: COMPANY SUCCESS AND INFLUENCING FACTORS (IQ3)

With IQ3 the respondents were asked to estimate their company’s success in the framework of three years. This question was broadened with asking them to compare the status of income generation, company’s brand value and customer value. Results (Table 6) show that customer value and brand value mainly contributed to the success of their companies. Most of the respondents evaluated their company status as increasing and achieving good results. Less respondents replied that the position of the company is in the phase of stagnation.

IQ9 requested the respondents to express their opinion about digital marketing and its importance for B2B companies. The respondents were asked to freely add also other factors that they deemed important. Table 7 shows that referrals or the word of mouth tactics is of crucial importance for the majority. The second most important theme was content.

Respondents also felt that their endeavours for satisfying customer needs can be rated as relatively successful.

IQ9								
Referral			Content			Satisfaction		
WOM	2	0,33%	events	1	0,16%	success	2	0,33%
recommer	1	0,16%	digital	9	1,47%	support	1	0,16%
referrals	6	0,98%	content	8	1,31%	challenge	3	0,49%
refer	3	0,49%	media	7	1,14%	well	1	0,16%
clients	5	0,82%	website	2	0,33%	good	4	0,65%
important	5	0,82%	stories	2	0,33%			
close	1	0,16%						
people	5	0,82%						
clients	5	0,82%						
TOTAL	31	5,06%	TOTAL	28	4,57%	TOTAL	11	1,47%

TABLE 7: IMPORTANT MARKETING TACTICS FOR B2B

Word cloud

Transcripts of relevant open-ended questions were imported and the text was analysed for the frequency of most often used nouns and adjectives. The word cloud tool provides an easy analysis of most frequently used terms. After filtering the text pool several terms were exposed as most frequently used. Figure 21 shows notions that were mentioned three to seven times. Some of the terms are similar or synonymous in meaning. The most powerful five notions with solid background in the opinion of respondents could thus be listed: (1) content, (2) referrals,(3) brand, (4) social and (5) media.

“It is not B2B, B2C, but B2I or business to interest.”

“The challenge in B2B is the mindset of people and their understanding how marketing or social media work.”

If companies want to succeed or stay successful on a long-term basis, they will need to reconsider their existing modus operandi and their philosophy. Frequently companies do not face difficulties because of technical challenges, but because of their internal culture and because they have not listened to the constantly changing world around them.

SUMMARY

The first part of the thesis reviewed the topics of digital marketing, sales success and the B2B aspect of selling products. Many authors researched individual topics, but few tried to understand how they are co-dependent or complementary. In this way our research has the potential to bring positive contribution to knowledge.

The concept of digital marketing is to engage customers in the online environment in order to make sales. While finishing the initial sales, the long-term goal is to manage profitable relationships for a longer period of time. Buyers should become brands' advocates and help co-create brands and thus increase their values. The theoretical overview further on showed that brands are a differentiating factor, but still not everything. Customer experience of today is modified and of bigger importance. To support it, marketers will need to choose a cleverly balanced marketing mix so that the buyer can make an informed purchase that might be repeated several times or referred to others.

Digital channels are prioritized over traditional ones for the majority of the industry. This subsequently lead to the main research question of the thesis: How does online marketing strategy affect sales success of B2B companies? There were not many researches about efficient digital marketing approaches for B2B and this logically lead to drawing parallels with the B2C segment or talking about digital marketing specifics in general. It was inferred that there could be a crucial connection between strategy, sales success and digital marketing. Bain's B2B elements of value presented a new insight into the mechanism of business-to-business. At the same time that pyramid presents a trajectory for profitable long-term growth.

The empirical part is a basic evaluation of the B2B digital marketing situation for some Slovene and Austrian companies with (at least) European reach.

FINDINGS

The research investigated the relation between digital marketing and the success of B2B companies. Further it was interesting to test what company goals lead to success and what key digital marketing strategies lead to it as well.

The next intention was to be even more specific and check what digital marketing strategies ensure the success of B2B companies.

Results show that 82% (strongly) agree that digital marketing positively affects success of B2B companies.

All respondents confirmed that income generation is the most important company goal and customer value the second one.

Crucial digital strategies that lead to sales success are good corporate website, social media and SEO. Similar available studies contrastingly placed content marketing first and websites second.

It was shown that the biggest share of marketing budgets go for digital advertising. The traditional offline marketing still holds the second place, whereas social media marketing and content marketing follow as third.

According to this research and the researches from the theoretical overview, **websites** are the most important selling factor. It was therefore interesting to see what elements on the website affect sales. There are two winning factors: transparent product details and excellent support. According to the evaluation of respondents low prices do not have a big value. They do on the other hand suggest improvements in providing good user experience.

LIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH

As presented in Chapter 3.5 there were several biases that were considered before the research, but it needs to be stressed that the research results showed also some limitations.

It might be that the sample chosen is not entirely representative for the B2B population. Some of the respondents work in companies that serve B2B and B2C.

Further on, their positions might limit them to getting detailed company information of relevance to our research.

The respondents could not prepare in advance for the questions, it might be that the evaluations are of subjective nature and do not base on actual data (e.g. when asking the respondents to allocate their marketing budgets among different channels).

Due to the fact that some of the respondents personally know the interviewer, it needs to be stressed that the social desirability bias could have led to more positive results. Next to that there is also the limitation of the researcher not being skilled in forming research questions and conducting professional interviews.

CONCLUSION

Through the literature review presented in this section an overview of the most important notions related to digital marketing and B2B sales has been made. On the foundations of theoretical definitions different views of authors or their research have been presented. Since everything connected to the digital world changes fast, all endeavours have been made to find the most recent findings, theoretic backgrounds or relevant guidelines. This proved to be rather difficult since B2B marketing segment is not abundant in researches, especially not with those related to digital marketing affecting sales success, better B2B customer or brand value. This might be due to four different factors:

- A. B2B companies see marketing in general, but digital marketing in particular, as inferior and less important therefore not much data is available,
- B. digital marketing strategies are prepared by external agencies,
- C. companies do not wish to share sensitive information that other B2B competitors might use to their advantage, or
- D. the phenomena of digital marketing affecting B2B segment is relatively young and therefore not mainstream for the B2B population.

Nevertheless, the theoretical research helped us infer the following:

- A. Due to tight competition and low differentiation, brand is a major value driver. Companies should place brand building as one of their key goals and integrate brand vision in CX.
- B. Customer-centric experiences generate better profitability.
- C. Quality data, upon which decisions are made, are only data that can be measured. Digital marketing platforms need to have good analytics.
- D. People are the most important frontline. Personnel's skills are the most efficient marketing and sales tool also when the digital is in question.

With the theoretical overview we have thus managed to partly answer three research questions: RQ2 (main goals of companies wanting to be successful), RQ3 (key online strategies) and RQ4 (the most efficient and appropriate usage of online marketing). A further insight will be provided with the analytical part and interviews. The main research question (RQ1: How does the usage of online marketing strategies influence the success of B2B companies) has been partly answered by providing some relevant researches, the specific target of Slovene and Austrian B2B companies will be profoundly answered with the analytical part presented in Chapters 3 and 4 of this thesis

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ANNEXURE

Dear ,ma'am/sir

The following questions about the influence of digital marketing on the success of companies will help us understand the influence of current marketing trends. The focus are B2B companies. Your feedback would be most appreciated.

This will take approximately 20 minutes of your time. Thank you.

SANDEEP KUMAR, MBA candidate at GALGOTIAS UNIVERSITY.

You can reach me at :baliyansandeep01@1gmail.com

You can expect three sections. The first set of questions will help us understand why your company is successful and how much digital marketing contributes to your company's success. You will help us determine what goals or activities are the most important.

IQ1: How important are goals for your company's success? Please rank each goal below accordingly.

	Not important at all	Not important	Of medium importance	Important	Very important	I do not know
Income generation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Brand building	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Customer value	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Launching new products	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Do you have other company goals? Please suggest.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

IQ2: To what extent do you agree with the following statement: "We are more successful since we have started using digital marketing for promotion."

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree
- I do not know

IQ3: Can you compare your current company's success with that of 3 years ago? Try to compare the status of income generation, company's brand value and customer value. If you have other factors influencing your success, you can comment on that as well. Explain shortly.

Let us move on to the second part. It is about digital marketing and digital channels.

IQ4: What digital channels influence your sales most? Please rank each channel according to its importance.

	Not important at all	Not important	Of medium importance	Important	Very important	I do not know
Content marketing	<input type="radio"/>					
Good corporate website	<input type="radio"/>					
Email marketing	<input type="radio"/>					
Social media (e.g. LinkedIn)	<input type="radio"/>					
PPC (pay per click) search marketing	<input type="radio"/>					
Online video (e.g. webinars, video explainers)	<input type="radio"/>					
Organic search marketing (SEO)	<input type="radio"/>					
Display advertising	<input type="radio"/>					
Affiliate marketing (e.g. a company pays compensation to third-party publishers to generate traffic)	<input type="radio"/>					
Development of micro sites or landing pages	<input type="radio"/>					
Mobile applications	<input type="radio"/>					
Mobile messaging	<input type="radio"/>					
Other. Please suggest:	<input type="radio"/>					

IQ5: Please allocate your company's planned budget among digital channels below. The total sum should be 100%.

E-mail marketing	<input type="text"/>
SEO	<input type="text"/>
Content marketing	<input type="text"/>
Digital commerce	<input type="text"/>
Digital advertising	<input type="text"/>
Offline advertising	<input type="text"/>
Customer analytics	<input type="text"/>
Website	<input type="text"/>
Social marketing	<input type="text"/>
Market research	<input type="text"/>
Mobile marketing	<input type="text"/>
Other	<input type="text"/>

If you chose the category "other" , please specify what other digital channel(s) you are using in your company.

What follows is the third part. Digital marketing affects the success of a company. Please share your views on this.

IQ6: Marketing activities positively impact revenue. Please rate the impact of the activities below.

	Not important at all	Not important	Of medium importance	Important	Very important	I do not know
SEO	<input type="radio"/>					
Word-of-mouth/referrals	<input type="radio"/>					
Trade shows, in-person events	<input type="radio"/>					
Calling prospective clients via call centers	<input type="radio"/>					
Customer visits	<input type="radio"/>					
Search advertising	<input type="radio"/>					
Content marketing	<input type="radio"/>					
Partner marketing	<input type="radio"/>					
Social media	<input type="radio"/>					
Sponsorships	<input type="radio"/>					
Marketing automation software	<input type="radio"/>					

Let us move on to specifics. Company websites are a vital instrument of customer information and service.

IQ7: What is the most important factor of your website that influences your customer's purchase?

	Not important at all	Not important	Of medium importance	Important	Very important	I do not know
Transparent product details	<input type="radio"/>					
Personalized recommendations	<input type="radio"/>					
Broad selection of products	<input type="radio"/>					
Consistently low prices	<input type="radio"/>					
Excellent support	<input type="radio"/>					
Other. Please specify.	<input type="radio"/>					

Could we touch also the subject of content marketing? It is a marketing technique for creating valuable content to attract new customers. In principle good content helps audience choose a product; it does not sell directly.

IQ8: What types of content does your company use for content marketing purposes? Several answers are possible.

- Social media posts
- Case studies
- Videos
- Ebooks/white papers
- Photos
- Other. Please specify.

IQ9: We would love to hear your ideas about digital marketing and its importance for B2B companies.

Now we are at the end. Can you please share some demographic details about your position and your company?

IQ10: What is your position in the company?

- Top management
- Senior management
- Middle management

IQ11: What segment are you in?

- B2B
- B2B and B2C
- B2C

IQ12: What is your company's annual turnover?

- up to 1 million €
- from 1 to 3 million €
- more than 3 million €

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CEC - Academic Writing

Announcements About the Course Ask a Question Progress Mentor Review Assignment

SANDEEP KUMAR

Date enrolled: 2022-02-10
 Email: sandeep.20gsob2010091@gaigotiasuniversity.edu.in
 Name: SANDEEP KUMAR

Assessment scores

Week 1 Graded Quiz/ Assignment	100.0
Week 2 Graded Assessment	100.0
Week 3 Graded Assessment	100.0
Week 4 Graded Assessment	65.0
First Subjective Assignment 2021 July	-
Week 5 Graded Assessment	70.0

Course outline

- Warm up activity
- Week 1 Academic and Research Writing
- Week 2 English in academic writing
- Week 3 Plagiarism in Academic Integrity
- Week 4 Journal Metrics
- Week 5 Author Metrics
- Week 6: Literature review I
- Week 7 Literature Review II
- Week 8 Review paper writing

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Week 8 Review paper writing

Week 9 Writing a research article

Week 10 Referencing, Submission & Post Submission

WEEK 11 THESIS WRITING

WEEK 12 EMPIRICAL STUDIES

Week 13 Challenges in Academic Writing & Team Management

Week 14: Other Major Academic Writings

Week 15 OERs: Use and Development

Academic Writing: Live Webinars (for reference only)

Bonus Week: Research & Publication Ethics (Remaining Topics)

Week 5 Graded Assessment	70.0
Week 6 Graded Assessment	100.0
WEEK 7 GRADED QUIZ	100.0
Week 8: Weekly Assignment	100.0
Week 9: Weekly Assignment	100.0
WEEK 10 FINAL GRADED Assessment	100.0
Week 11 GRADED QUIZ	50.0
Week 12 Graded Quiz	80.0
Second Subjective Assignment Jan 2022	100.0
Week 13 Graded Quiz	80.0
Week 14 Graded Quiz	60.0
Week 15 Graded Quiz	50.0

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Academic Writing - Course

onlinecourses.wyam2.ac.in/ce22_g603/subjective/naame214

Second Subjective Assignment: Jan 2022

Due on 2022-05-01, 23:59 IST
Maximum size of assignment : 5 MB

Course outline

- Warm up activity
- Week 1 Academic and Research Writing
- Week 2 English in academic writing
- Week 3 Plagiarism in Academic Integrity
- Week 4 Journal Metrics
- Week 5 Author Metrics
- Week 6: Literature review I
- Week 7 Literature Review II
- Week 8 Review paper writing
- Week 9 Writing a research article
- Week 10 Referencing, Submission & Post

Dear learner,
Please complete a short course (of about 1 hr) "Literature Search & Reference Management in Academic Writing" URL: <https://pharmastate.academy/courses/literature-search-reference-managements/> and upload the course certificate as assignment. Please follow the following steps:
Step 1: go to <https://pharmastate.academy/courses/literature-search-reference-managements/>
Step 2: Login to this course (contact academy@pharmastate.com, 8557874143 if any problem is there).
Step 3: Complete this 42 mins course, complete this course quiz.
Step 4: Generate and download the course completion certificate
Step 5: upload the certificate here
(click add file -> browse and select the certificate file-> click submit)
THE LAST DATE (01/05/22) IS NOT AT ALL GOING TO BE EXTENDED IN ANY CASE
PLEASE ALSO NOTE THAT YOU WON'T BE ABLE TO SEE THE SCORE UNTILL ALL THE EVALUATIONS ARE OVER. SO PLEASE DONT COMMUNICATE FOR THE SCORE TILL SECOND WEEK OF May 2022.

In the course, only one, out of the two subjective assignments, is mandatory. Therefore if you have submitted the first subjective assignment, you need NOT to do this one. Remember! only once the file can be uploaded. So, be careful. No communication shall be entertained for wrong upload.

Your Submission:

The due date for submitting the assignment has passed.
Assignment submitted on 2022-05-01, 22:52 IST

SANDEEP KUMAR 2063062011091 CER ACADEMIC WI. pdf

Certificate

OF ACHIEVEMENT

This is to certify that

SANDEEP KUMAR

has successfully completed 42 minutes online course of
Literature Search & Reference Management in Academic Writing
on 01/05/2022

Valid Certificate ID

3ee21da816d779b8

Dr. Ajay Semalty, PharmaState Academy
PharmaState Academy

PLAGIARISM REPORT

93% Unique Content	7% Plagiarized content	✓ COMPLETED
<p>Sentence wise results Matched URLs</p>		
unique	RESEARCH MEATHODOLOGY The study was conducted through the online mode through google form.	
unique	Questionnaire google link was prepared and shared and responses were collected thro...	
unique	Data used was collected through the primary research which was taken through google link.	
unique	Source:- Data was collected through responses of the questionnaire and for few resp...	
unique	Sampling Procedure:- Sampling procedure used was a random sampling.	
unique	All observation had equal likelihood to get selected.	
unique	Sample Size:- 135 responses were collected from the customers from print media indu...	
unique	65 responses were collected from respondents who are currently working in the print...	
unique	Period of study: The study period which was chosen was 1st July 2021 to 1st Septemb...	
unique	RESEARCH OBJECTIVES • To find if the magazine content and physical design of the ma...	
unique	• To find if the loyalty programmes affects the repurchase rate.	
unique	• To find how the print media industry utilizes its framework for CUSTOMER RESEARCH.	
unique	• To find out all the factors which influences the repurchase rate.	
unique	Analyzing Objective 1 RESEARCH ANALYSIS Extended Subscription Key book or guide boo...	
unique	7 purchase 36 10 25 5 to 7 purchase 18 7 14 4 or less purchase 5 4	
unique	3 The y axis in the above table shows the repurchase rate of the customer.	
unique	The x axis shows the different loyalty programmes which influences the repurchase rate.	
unique	Technique used: Chi-Square Method Hypothesis:- Null Hypothesis : H0- : Loyalty Pro...	

About Plagiarism Checker

Plagiarism detection is the process of locating instances of **plagiarism** within a work or document. The widespread use of computers and the advent of the Internet has made it easier to **plagiarize** the work of others. Most cases of **plagiarism** are found in academia, where documents are typically essays or reports.

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Acceptance Letter

Dated: 12/05/2022

Dear Authors,

We are glad to inform you that your paper has been accepted as per our fast peer review process:

Authors Name: Sandeep Kumar

Paper Title: Influence of Online Marketing Strategies on the Sales Success of B2B Companies

Paper Status: Accepted

Paper Id: IJ-1205221250

for possible publication in **International Journal of All Research Education & Scientific Methods, (IJARESM), ISSN No: 2455-6211”, Impact Factor : 7.429,**

in the current Issue, **Volume 10, Issue 5, May - 2022.**

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